

The OpenAlex database in review: Evaluating its applications, capabilities, and limitations

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Abstract: This systematic review examines OpenAlex, focusing on its technical features and its applications within science studies and scientific information sources. The paper offers a critical perspective on OpenAlex's role in democratizing and promoting equity in access to scientific information. A total of 146 articles published between 2022 and 2025 are analyzed and classified by functionality and application, including AI-based validation processes. Findings reveal the rapid adoption of OpenAlex as an open alternative to commercial databases, particularly across the Global South. However, notable metadata limitations—especially regarding affiliations, languages, and document types—still affect analytical reliability. The study highlights key opportunities and challenges for researchers, libraries, institutions, and the technical community, emphasizing the need for complementary validation and responsible assessment strategies.

Keywords: OpenAlex, systematic review, science studies, scientific information sources, metadata quality, scientific infrastructure, Global South, open science, bibliometrics, research evaluation

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1. Introduction

In the context of open science, access to free bibliographic data has become a strategic element to ensure transparency, traceability, and equity in research. For decades, bibliometric analyses and academic assessment have relied on commercial databases such as Web of Science (Institute for Scientific Information) and Scopus (Elsevier), whose high costs and usage restrictions have limited access in many settings and exacerbated regional and institutional inequalities (Korte et al., 2023; Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). This dependence on proprietary platforms not only conditions access to scientific information but also introduces biases in document coverage and derived indicators, which may compromise the representativeness and international comparability of evaluation results. Furthermore, the economic barriers imposed by these tools tend to deepen asymmetries among geographic regions, institutions, and scientific communities, hampering the development of local capacities for bibliometric analysis and reducing opportunities for innovation in the management of scientific knowledge.

43 In this context, open alternatives have emerged to reduce dependence on proprietary platforms.
44 Among them, OpenAlex stands out as a successor to Microsoft Academic Graph, launched in
45 2022 by OurResearch. With over 250 million indexed publications and links to 90 million
46 authors and 100,000 institutions, its design based on persistent identifiers (DOI, ORCID, ROR)
47 facilitates interoperability and large-scale analysis (Akbaritabar et al., 2024; Simard et al.,
48 2024). OpenAlex has been incorporated into platforms such as the Open Science Observatory
49 (EOSC, 2023) and is recognized as a resource aligned with responsible assessment agendas
50 (Moed et al., 2022). At the institutional level, its growing use is reflected in initiatives such as
51 the adoption of open-source solutions. In 2023, Sorbonne University cancelled Clarivate's
52 commercial tools to adopt OpenAlex and other open-source solutions (Commitments to Open
53 Science, n.d.). Similarly, Leiden University publishes the Leiden Ranking Open Edition based
54 exclusively on open data from OpenAlex (CWTS Leiden Ranking Open Edition).

55 Given this growing institutional adoption, recent literature on OpenAlex combines two main
56 approaches. Numerous studies employ it as a data source for systematic reviews, bibliometric
57 analyses, and information services across multiple fields (Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025;
58 Laakso, 2023; Maddi et al., 2024). To a lesser extent, research focuses on comparing its
59 technical functionality against WoS, Scopus, and Dimensions.ai, assessing coverage, metadata
60 accuracy, and interoperability. Findings reveal strengths in linguistic coverage and the
61 representation of diamond open access journals (Simard et al., 2024), but also persistent
62 limitations in language metadata, institutional affiliation, and document typologies (Canto et
63 al., 2024; Céspedes et al., 2025; Delgado Quirós & Ortega, 2023). These mixed findings
64 underscore that, while OpenAlex shows considerable promise, Visser et al. (2021) recommend
65 combining sources to achieve broader coverage and greater reliability in bibliometric studies,
66 reaffirming the importance of critically assessing the role of OpenAlex within this ecosystem.

67 Despite the growing body of research, no systematic synthesis of the literature on OpenAlex
68 has so far integrated both perspectives: the evaluation of its technical infrastructure and its
69 application in bibliometric and knowledge management contexts. This study aims to fill this
70 gap by means of a systematic literature review (SLR), with three objectives:

- 71 1. To identify and classify scientific output on OpenAlex, distinguishing
72 between studies focused on the evaluation of its technical
73 functionalities and those aimed at its applications in bibliometric
74 contexts.
- 75 2. To systematically analyse the main findings as well as the
76 methodological and technical limitations reported in the recent
77 literature on OpenAlex.
- 78 3. To discuss the practical implications of OpenAlex for different user
79 profiles, considering opportunities, challenges, and specific
80 recommendations derived from the reviewed evidence.

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82 **2. Methodology**

83 *2.1 Search strategy and study selection criteria*

84 A systematic qualitative methodology was adopted, involving the identification, analysis, and
85 synthesis of relevant content from scientific publications. The structured search strategy
86 covered major databases specializing in bibliographic and scientific information, including
87 OpenAlex, Dimensions, Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed, and Library and Information
88 Science Abstracts (LISA). At every stage, the procedures followed the guidelines of the
89 PRISMA 2020 statement for systematic reviews and meta-analyses (Page et al., 2021). The

90 search string used was: (title OR abstract OR keywords = "OpenAlex") AND document type =
 91 articles. Record downloads were conducted between 14 February and 18 March 2025, which
 92 constitutes the temporal cutoff point for this review (Figure 1).
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94 *Fig. 1: PRISMA flow diagram for the identification, screening, and inclusion of studies on OpenAlex.*
 95 *Diagram generated with H161diagrams software¹*

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97 For this systematic review, only articles published in scientific journals that addressed analyses
 98 (quantitative or qualitative) of the OpenAlex database or used it as an information source for
 99 diverse research purposes, such as bibliometric studies, were included. Abstracts, conference
 100 presentations, editorials, theses, and any documents lacking full-text access or not constituting
 101 original research articles were excluded. The identification process was conducted in
 102 successive and coordinated stages, beginning with the detection of articles through the analysis
 103 of titles, abstracts, and keywords in each database. Subsequently, duplicate records were
 104 removed. Finally, full texts were assessed to verify their eligibility and relevance according to
 105 the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

106 2.2. Creation of a classification system

107 For the classification of studies included in this review, two main categories were considered:
 108 (1) studies evaluating the functionalities of OpenAlex and (2) studies using OpenAlex as a
 109 source of bibliometric information. Subcategories were incorporated under each main category.
 110 The expert classification was performed through the review of abstracts and further validated
 111 using artificial intelligence (ChatGPT). The criteria adopted for classification were as follows:

¹ H161diagrams, with interactivity for optimised digital transparency and Open Synthesis Campbell Systematic Reviews, 18, e1230. <https://doi.org/10.1002/c12.1230>

112 **1. Functional analysis of OpenAlex:** This category comprises studies whose primary
 113 objective is to examine, assess, or improve the database itself (including its structure,
 114 quality, tools, or performance). The assigned subcategories are detailed in Table
 115 **2. Applications and use of OpenAlex:** This category includes works that employ
 116 OpenAlex as a data source for conducting research, offering services, or performing
 117 external analyses. The assigned subcategories are detailed in Table 1.

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Table 1. Main categories and assigned subcategories for each classification.

Code	Definition
1. Functional analysis of OpenAlex	
1.1 Coverage studies	Studies that assess the comprehensiveness of the OpenAlex database in relation to other databases (such as WoS, Scopus, PubMed, Dimensions) or based on specific characteristics: country, discipline, language, period, etc.
1.2 Metadata accuracy	Includes studies that evaluate the quality, consistency, and reliability of metadata in OpenAlex. The focus is on fields such as authors, affiliations, unique identifiers (DOI, ORCID), references, or funding entities.
1.3 Other functionalities	Studies that examine structural, operational, or technical aspects of the OpenAlex system, excluding metadata. This includes data architecture, interoperability, licensing, API performance, latency, or system stability.
1.4 Document characterization	Includes studies that quantitatively describe the internal composition of OpenAlex in terms of document type, language, open access status, citation counts, co-authorship networks, temporal distribution, or other document attributes.
1.5 Publication quality	Includes studies that evaluate the overall robustness and reliability of OpenAlex as an academic information system. This analyzes issues such as duplications, false or inconsistent records, critical gaps, or systemic biases.
1.6 Tutorials and APIs	Includes studies, technical articles, reports, or educational materials that develop, evaluate, or explain how to access OpenAlex using programmatic tools such as its REST API, SDKs, wrappers in R, Python, or other languages.
2. Applications and use of OpenAlex	
2.1 Systematic review	Studies that use OpenAlex as a source for systematic reviews following recognized protocols (PRISMA, JBI, etc.)
2.2 Narrative review	Narrative reviews, thematic mappings, or state-of-the-art studies that use OpenAlex as a data source, without applying a formal protocol.
2.3 Descriptive bibliometrics	Studies that use OpenAlex to apply bibliometric indicators, co-authorship networks, citation analyses, or metrics, without evaluating the database or developing tools.
2.4 Libraries and institutional services	Studies that develop, introduce, or evaluate platforms, dashboards, APIs, visualization systems, or reproducible technical methodologies aimed at providing bibliometric services. Also includes studies that integrate or evaluate the use of OpenAlex in libraries, evaluation offices, institutional repositories, or academic support services
2.5 Science and society	Studies that use OpenAlex data to analyse the relationship between scientific production and social, cultural, or political dynamics. This encompasses research on gender, language, or regional biases, the representation of knowledge in media and digital platforms, and inequalities in circulation and epistemic recognition.

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123 2.3. Validation and review with ChatGPT

124 Once the articles were classified according to the criteria in Table 1, the reliability of the
125 process was strengthened by performing validation with generative artificial intelligence using
126 ChatGPT and its GPT-4o model. The validation was performed in two stages. In the first stage
127 (primary classification), a file with 146 records (ID, title, and abstract in the original language)
128 was provided to the model. The two possible categories (1. Functional analysis, 2. Applications
129 and uses) and the criteria established for the classification (Table 1) were indicated, clarifying
130 that, in this primary category, an article could only belong to one of them. The result was 104
131 matches with the manual classification (71.2%) and 42 discrepancies (28.8%). After expert
132 review, 3 automatic proposals were accepted, retaining the manual classification in 39 cases.
133 In the second stage (secondary classification), the model was asked to assign the corresponding
134 subcategories within each primary category (e.g., 1.1 Coverage studies, 1.2 Metadata accuracy,
135 2.1 Systematic reviews, 2.3 Descriptive bibliometrics, etc.). In this phase, the model was
136 instructed to perform a deep semantic analysis of the abstracts, so that the classification would
137 not depend exclusively on lexical matches. It was specified that in the secondary classification,
138 each document could have more than one subcategory.

139 The comparison between manual and automatic classification reveals systematic discrepancies:
140 full matches are marginal, and there is a prevalence of over-assignment by AI in the Descriptive
141 bibliometrics category (2.3), with notable confusion between Libraries and institutional
142 services (2.4) and Descriptive bibliometrics (2.3) (48 cases). Furthermore, the classification
143 performed by generative AI reveals frequent errors between Systematic reviews (2.1) and
144 Narrative reviews (2.2), and misassignments of Tutorials and APIs (1.6) and Publication
145 quality (1.5) to Descriptive bibliometrics (2.3), suggesting that the model prioritizes superficial
146 signals over conceptual features. These patterns justify supervised calibration with curated
147 examples to reduce over-assignment and improve sensitivity in distinguishing between
148 functional evaluation and usage applications. Discrepancies were resolved after document
149 review and category reassignment when appropriate.

150 3. Results

151 3.1. Basic characteristics of the corpus

152 The analysed corpus comprises 146 articles published between 2022 and 2025, with a clear
153 concentration in 2024 (59.6%). Editorial dissemination is heterogeneous: on one hand,
154 consolidated scientometric and bibliometric journals such as *Scientometrics* (4.79% of the
155 corpus), *Quantitative Science Studies* (2.74%), and *Journal of Documentation* (1.37%); on the
156 other, international open access platforms like PLOS ONE, F1000Research, and Scientific
157 Data, which together account for nearly 5% of the articles. Added to this core is a block of
158 Latin American publications—including *Ciência da Informação*, *Revista Multidisciplinar do*
159 *Nordeste Mineiro*, *Revista Interamericana de Bibliotecología*, *Información, cultura y sociedad*,
160 *Investigación Bibliotecológica*, *El Profesional de la Información*, and *Discursos del Sur*—
161 which accounts for 6.16% of the articles, demonstrating the early adoption of OpenAlex in the
162 Global South and reinforcing its nature as a global open access infrastructure.

163 Within this framework, the thematic classification (Table 2) shows that most works fall under
164 category 2. *Applications and uses* (80.82%), with a predominance of analyses of bibliometric
165 databases (57.5% of the total) and, secondly, studies on science and society (30.1%). OpenAlex
166 has been used primarily as a working tool for bibliometric research, while contributions
167 focused on its functionality represent 19.18% of the corpus, with emphasis on metadata
168 accuracy (11% of the total) and coverage (8.2% of the total). Below, we will analyse in detail
169 each of the sections included in the classification.

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Table 2. Distribution of articles on OpenAlex by category and subcategory (n=146)

Main category	Subcategory	No. of articles	% within block	% of total sample
Functional analysis 19.18% (n=28)	1.1 Coverage studies	12	42.9%	8.2%
	1.2 Metadata accuracy	16	57.1%	11%
	1.3 Other functionalities	7	25.00%	4.8%
	1.4 Document characterization	4	14.3%	2.7%
	1.5 Publication quality	8	28.6%	5.5%
	1.6 Tutorials and APIs	2	7.1%	1.37%
Applications and uses 80.82% (n=118)	2.1 Systematic reviews	22	18.6%	15.1%
	2.2 Narrative reviews	12	10.2%	8.2%
	2.3 Descriptive bibliometrics	84	71.2%	57.5%
	2.4 Libraries and institutional services	5	4.2%	3.4%
	2.5 Science and society	44	37.3%	30.1%

171 *Note: The same article may belong to more than one subcategory, so the percentages within each block do not necessarily add up to 100%*

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173 3.2 Studies evaluating OpenAlex functionality

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175 Table 3. Functional analysis subcategories: findings and references ordered by publication volume

Subcategory	Finding summary	Main references
1.2 metadata accuracy	Advances in open metadata, though with limitations: errors in language identification (15%), gaps in institutional affiliations (>60%), and inaccurate assignments in document type and concepts. Accuracy varies by language and field, so complementary validation is recommended.	(Céspedes et al., 2025; Delgado Quirós & Ortega, 2023; Delgado-Quirós & Ortega, 2024; Gallardo & Bruccoleri Ochoa, 2024; Jiao et al., 2023; Schares, 2024; Scheidsteger et al., 2023; Scheidsteger & Haunschild, 2023; Singh et al., 2024; Velez-Estevez et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024)
1.1 Coverage studies	Provides broader coverage than WoS and Scopus in non-English languages, social sciences, humanities, and regional publications (Latin America, Eastern Europe). However, omissions remain regarding affiliations, funding metadata, advanced metrics, and thematic hierarchies, with performance still lower than commercial databases in some structural aspects.	(Canto et al., 2024; Céspedes et al., 2025; Delgado Quirós & Ortega, 2023; Harder, 2024; Ivanić, 2024; Macêdo et al., 2024; Shemilt et al., 2024; Stankovic et al., 2025; Velez-Estevez et al., 2023)
1.5 Publication quality	Reproduces editorial biases and has limitations in detecting retracted documents. The integration of multiple sources may result in loss of information, although methodological openness facilitates external audits.	(Delgado Quirós & Ortega, 2023; Delgado-Quirós & Ortega, 2024; Gusenbauer, 2024; Scheidsteger et al., 2023; Tsiura, 2024; Van Bellen, 2024)
1.4 Document characterization	Provides broad and diverse coverage in languages, open access, types, and disciplines, with better representation of underrepresented areas (social sciences, humanities, Spanish-language publications, diamond open access journals). However, completeness of basic metadata (volume, number, pages) remains lacking due to source integration.	(Delgado-Quirós & Ortega, 2024; Gallardo & Bruccoleri Ochoa, 2024; Simard et al., 2024)
1.3 Other functionalities and 1.6 Tutorials and APIs	Stands out for its open access, robust API, and tools for automated extraction and analysis (e.g., openalexR). However, automatic categorization shows limitations in certain fields (environmental sciences, arts), reducing retrieval accuracy. Its API functionalities are competitive with commercial platforms, though with lower performance in advanced queries and metrics.	(Aria et al., 2024; Borrego, 2024; Harder, 2024; Ivanić, 2024; Macêdo et al., 2024; Rose et al., 2025; Shemilt et al., 2024; Stankovic et al., 2025; Velez-Estevez et al., 2023).

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177 Several studies have pointed out limitations in the completeness of institutional metadata in
178 OpenAlex. Delgado-Quirós & Ortega (2024) identified completeness rates below 60%, while
179 Zhang et al. (2024) and Van Bellen (2024) reported similar proportions, affecting the
180 geographic traceability of scientific production. Regarding document typology, Jiao et al.
181 (2023) observed that the genre data paper is classified as a scientific article, hindering its
182 differentiated retrieval. Simard et al. (2024) show that OpenAlex indexes most DOAJ journals
183 (89%), including 87% of diamond open access and 95% of gold open access, with coverage
184 notably superior to WoS and Scopus; additionally, OpenAlex collects a higher proportion of
185 multilingual diamond journals than WoS Core Collection, indicating a less pronounced
186 language bias, although Céspedes et al. (2025) showed uneven performance in automatic
187 language assignment. On the other hand, studies highlight the broad coverage of research with
188 a regional focus, including publications from Eastern Europe, the Global South, and Southern
189 regions in disciplines related to the social sciences and humanities that are often
190 underrepresented in Scopus and WoS (Gallardo & Bruccoleri, 2024).

191 Beyond metadata quality issues, analyses on publication quality consistently point out
192 limitations related to the detection of retracted documents, duplications, and editorial errors.
193 Stankovic et al. (2025) showed that the database identifies only a fraction of the retractions
194 listed in Retraction Watch, revealing inconsistencies in source integration. Problems have also
195 been documented in duplication, citation assignment errors, and significant gaps in
196 bibliographic metadata, affecting the reliability of derived indicators (Mongeon et al., 2023;
197 Ortega & Delgado-Quirós, 2024). Delgado Quirós & Ortega (2023) also found substantive
198 variations in normalized metrics obtained with OpenAlex compared to other databases, due to
199 metadata errors and coverage biases. Comparative analyses have indicated that OpenAlex tends
200 to overestimate the number of references, although it is praised for its ability to integrate with
201 other open sources and databases (Gusenbauer, 2024; Scheidsteger et al., 2023).

202 Despite these quality concerns, recent studies note that OpenAlex improves the visibility of
203 scientific production in emerging countries and underrepresented disciplines, such as social
204 sciences and humanities. Gallardo & Bruccoleri Ochoa (2024) and Canto et al. (2024) show
205 greater coverage than WoS and Scopus for publications from Eastern Europe and South
206 America, including local journals and those without DOIs. However, problems have also been
207 recorded in assigning institutional affiliations, such as for Argentine authors with dual
208 affiliations (Gallardo & Bruccoleri Ochoa, 2024). Zhang et al. (2024) confirmed that 61.5% of
209 records lack affiliations, with biases that negatively affect certain publishers and regions.
210 Regarding language, Van Bellen (2024), comparing articles published by Canadian authors,
211 notes that while OpenAlex also favours English (67% vs. 55% for French), Dimensions.ai
212 offers a much higher coverage level for French content. Céspedes et al. (2025) conclude that
213 OpenAlex offers more balanced linguistic coverage than WoS, with 68% of articles in English
214 and 32% in other languages.

215 From a technical perspective, OpenAlex has enabled a set of technical and analytical
216 functionalities beyond basic information retrieval, promoting its adoption as bibliographic data
217 infrastructure, particularly through its applications (API)² (Velez-Estevez et al., 2023). The
218 practical utility of the openalexR³ package for interacting with its API from the R language is
219 highlighted, enabling advanced queries, metadata extraction, and automated bibliometric
220 analysis (Aria et al., 2024; Borrego, 2024). Complementary systems such as API-CODEBASE⁴
221 have also been developed, allowing joint searches in multiple sources, combining data from

² [openalex-docs/how-to-use-the-api/api-overview.md](https://github.com/openalex-docs/how-to-use-the-api/api-overview.md) at main · ourresearch/openalex-docs · GitHub

³ [GitHub - ropensci/openalexR: Getting bibliographic records from OpenAlex](https://github.com/ropensci/openalexR)

⁴ [Using Scopus and OpenAlex APIs to retrieve bibliographic data for evidence synthesis. A procedure based on Bash and SQL - Mendely Data](#)

222 OpenAlex and Scopus (Harder, 2024). Other studies suggest that OpenAlex has weaknesses
 223 compared to commercial databases like Scopus or Dimensions.ai, especially in complex
 224 advanced searches and specialized metrics, such as altmetrics (Velez-Estevez et al., 2023).
 225 However, integrating OpenAlex into automated workflows—for example, systematic reviews
 226 or bibliometric maps—significantly improves efficiency and reduces costs compared to
 227 traditional methods (Shemilt et al., 2024)

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229 3.3. Studies on the applications and uses of OpenAlex

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231 *Table 4. Applications and Uses subcategories: findings and references organized by publication volume.*

Subcategory	Finding summary	Main references
2.3 Descriptive bibliometrics	Quantitative methods are employed to study productivity, co-authorship, citation networks, thematic evolution, and institutional mobility in areas such as health, sustainability, artificial intelligence, education, gender, and open science. OpenAlex is used as the main or combined source, notable for its open access and compatibility with tools like VOSviewer, bibliometrix, and chord diagrams.	(Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025; Arroyo-Machado & Costas, 2023; Batzdorfer et al., 2024; Hao et al., 2023; Haunschild & Bornmann, 2024; Jurowetzi et al., 2025; Klarak et al., 2025; Meng et al., 2024; Mongeon et al., 2023; Murillo-Gonzalez & López, 2023; Nguyen & Carraz, 2025; Pretolesi et al., 2025; Soto-Herrera et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2025).
2.5 Science and society	These studies examine the relationship between scientific production and society, focusing on open science, disciplinary biases, and structural gaps that especially affect countries in the Global South. They include analyses of sources such as Wikipedia and methodological proposals to assess asymmetries of power and recognition. In this context, OpenAlex is used both as a data source and as a critical tool to rethink the global scientific system.	(Akbaritabar et al., 2024; Arroyo-Machado et al., 2025; Arroyo-Machado & Costas, 2023; Giziński et al., 2024; Gomez et al., 2024; Kim et al., 2024; Kitajima & Okamura, 2025; Lewoniewski, 2024; Maddi et al., 2024; Soto-Herrera et al., 2025; Unzurrunzaga et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2025)
2. Systematic reviews	These studies focus on areas such as educational technologies, health, neuroscience, environmental conservation, epidemiology, and applied social sciences. OpenAlex is used as a primary or complementary source to broaden literature recovery, especially in fields with limited coverage in traditional databases, including grey literature and open access. The methodologies applied include thematic analysis, narrative synthesis, and co-occurrence networks.	(Aanesen et al., 2024; Ames et al., 2024; Arachchige et al., 2024; Bergdahl et al., 2024; Bond et al., 2024; Ferreira Aderaldo et al., 2023; Hollands et al., 2024)
2.2 Narrative reviews	Includes bibliographic studies that do not apply PRISMA protocols. These are descriptive reviews, syntheses of broad fields, or state-of-the-art overviews that do not seek to answer specific questions. Studies are included in areas such as education, mental health, management, accounting, food science, nutrition, and dietetics.	(De Sousa Silva & Alves De Sousa, 2024; Foderaro & Gunnarsson Lorentzen, 2024; Foley et al., 2025; Klarak et al., 2025; Nasir et al., 2024; Olenikova et al., 2025; Paidicán Soto & Arredondo Herrera, 2024; Tu Le et al., 2024)
2.4 Libraries and institutional services	Includes institutional developments based on OpenAlex. Examples are a bibliometric dashboard in Streamlit for strategic decision-making, a study on its adoption by librarians at Kastamonu University, and the Laguna project in Brazil, which integrates OpenAlex into a national open information infrastructure.	(Bayly et al., 2024; Derviş, 2025; Jahn, 2025; Neubert et al., 2024; Orner, 2024)

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236 Several studies use OpenAlex to examine the relationship between scientific dynamics and
237 power structures. Most of these works use OpenAlex as an information source to expose
238 inequalities, rethink indicators, and promote a more equitable scientific structure.
239 Akbaritabar et al. (2024) develop a methodology to track academic migration using Scopus
240 and OpenAlex data, revealing gaps in the representation of non-Western regions. Yang et al.
241 (2024) evaluate publication dynamics by discipline, and Yu et al. (2025) develop tools to
242 study academic mobility. Kim et al. (2024) and Xu et al. (2024) address gender and regional
243 biases in open access. Maddi et al. (2024) present prototypes for indexing LGBTQ+
244 knowledge with open sources.

245 Expanding on these critical perspectives, Arroyo-Machado et al. (2025) examine the use of
246 ORCID in Spain, highlighting disciplinary disparities and the impact of incomplete data on
247 equity in academic recognition. In this regard, Kitajima & Okamura (2025) propose methods
248 for enriching ORCID profiles with OpenAlex—an issue also addressed by Lewoniewski
249 (2024), who contributes indicators for evaluating data coverage and reliability. Regarding
250 access to scientific information, Soto-Herrera et al. (2025) examine the representation of
251 Latin American journals in OpenAlex, and at the national level, Unzurrunzaga et al. (2024)
252 apply OpenAlex to monitor open access in Argentina. Arroyo-Machado & Costas (2023)
253 explore the disconnect between academic interest and social attention by combining data
254 from OpenAlex and Wikipedia, revealing linguistic and conceptual biases. Giziński et al.
255 (2024) introduce metrics that quantify the propagation of units of meaning through citations
256 and co-authorships to assess discursive influence in the field. Gomez et al. (2024) map global
257 scientific ecosystems using ecological networks, showing how certain institutions dominate
258 visibility and citation.

259 Shifting from critical research to methodological applications, documents that include
260 systematic reviews, meta-analyses, and narrative reviews are grouped across various fields
261 of application. They predominantly focus on health and medicine, ranging from pain
262 treatments (Ames et al., 2024; De Sousa Filho & De Queiroz, 2024) and assisted reproduction
263 (Aderaldo et al., 2023) to neurology and rehabilitation (Hassan et al., 2024; Ilyas et al., 2024;
264 Marfina et al., 2024; Klarak et al., 2025) and mental health (Aanesen et al., 2024; De Sousa
265 Silva & De Sousa, 2024). In education, they cover the implementation of educational
266 programs (Librea et al., 2023), the use of technologies such as augmented reality and artificial
267 intelligence (AI) in learning (Adhe et al., 2024; Barrun & Gilbas, 2025; Bond et al., 2024;
268 Krasnopeyeva & Remkhe, 2024; Nasir et al., 2024; Paidicán Soto & Arredondo Herrera,
269 2024), and learning analytics (Bergdahl et al., 2024). The studies also extend to
270 environmental management and sustainability (Arachchige et al., 2024; Kpadé et al., 2024;
271 Oleinikova et al., 2025; Tu Le et al., 2024), research methodology and information science
272 (Foderaro & Gunnarsson Lorentzen, 2024; Hollands et al., 2024; Schmidt et al., 2021), and
273 social and economic sciences (Foley et al., 2025; Liventsova et al., 2024; Nurhasan et al.,
274 2024; Sudarsono et al., 2023). In all these contexts, OpenAlex is consistently used as a main
275 or complementary source for identifying and analysing academic literature, as a supplement
276 for grey literature (Aanesen et al., 2024; Foley et al., 2025), or for citation searches
277 (snowballing) (Bergdahl et al., 2024; Bond et al., 2024).

278 Beyond literature reviews, OpenAlex has been used to develop bibliometric tools and services,
279 becoming integrated into institutional platforms and workflows and promoting reproducible
280 practices. In library applications, Bayly et al. (2024) present an app built with the Streamlit
281 framework to visualize the impact of research infrastructure; Orner (2024) implements an
282 automated citation analysis methodology for library collections; and Jahn (2025) proposes an
283 open data-based approach to evaluate transformative agreements. In scientometrics,

284 Akbaritabar et al. (2024) develop a methodology for tracking academic migration with public
285 data and scripts; Okamura (2023) proposes a method for mapping global scientific
286 collaboration; and Pal & Mukhopadhyay (2024) implement an automatic classification tool for
287 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Collectively, these works show how OpenAlex drives
288 the development of open tools and reproducible methods in various contexts.

289 Representing the most common application type, most articles use OpenAlex in large-scale
290 bibliometric studies. These include analyses of publication trends and growth, which examine
291 the evolution of article volume over time (Adhe et al., 2024; Puspitasari et al., 2025). Thematic
292 and conceptual mapping is also conducted to reveal dominant and emerging research areas,
293 often using OpenAlex concepts to classify disciplines or subfields (Alnujaimi, 2024; Mazoni
294 et al., 2023; Pretolesi et al., 2024). Collaboration and citation network analysis is frequently
295 used to understand connections between authors, institutions, or journals (Segundo et al., 2024;
296 Akbaritabar et al., 2024; Moutinho et al., 2024; Yan et al., 2025). Similarly, studies address the
297 analysis of scientific mobility and diaspora by tracking researcher trajectories (Akbaritabar et
298 al., 2024; Carneiro et al., 2024; Luo & Hu, 2024). Impact and visibility analyses (Gomez et al.,
299 2024; Yang et al., 2023), as well as research on bias or equity in knowledge representation
300 (Castro Torres, 2025; Maddi et al., 2024; Soni & Roy, 2024), are also common. Lastly,
301 adoption and metadata completeness in profile systems like ORCID are evaluated (Arroyo-
302 Machado et al., 2025).

303 4. Discussion and final remarks

304 This work has presented a systematic review of OpenAlex, addressing both its technical
305 functionalities and the diversity of its uses in bibliometric research. The results show that
306 OpenAlex has quickly consolidated itself as a strategic open access infrastructure, positioning
307 itself as an attractive alternative to commercial databases such as Scopus and Web of Science.
308 However, significant limitations persist in metadata quality and completeness, coverage of
309 affiliations, and advanced interoperability, which condition its full utilization in certain
310 contexts. Although access is free, the lack of normalization and consistency in several fields
311 increases the costs of data processing and record cleaning, which in large-scale projects may
312 equal or even exceed the expenses associated with proprietary databases.

313 Building on these findings, the review identifies an imbalance between uses and evaluation of
314 functionalities: more than 80% of studies use OpenAlex as a source for bibliometric
315 applications, systematic reviews, or studies on science and society, while only 19% examine
316 its technical aspects. This pattern demonstrates rapid adoption for practical use and, at the same
317 time, the need to strengthen technical validation, particularly regarding affiliation, language,
318 and document type metadata, which condition the reliability of analyses. Early adoption is also
319 observed in the Global South—especially in Brazil, Argentina, and Colombia—since 2022,
320 both in bibliometric studies and in institutional services and open access projects. This
321 behaviour, more agile than that observed with commercial databases, reinforces OpenAlex's
322 global and inclusive reach by making visible regional literature, journals without DOIs, and
323 areas traditionally underrepresented such as social sciences and humanities.

324 Reflecting these differentiated patterns of use and adoption, OpenAlex offers opportunities and
325 limitations for distinct user profiles. As summarized in Table 5, researchers gain expanded
326 access to traditionally restricted literature and can more readily incorporate preprints and grey
327 literature, though challenges remain regarding metadata errors and partial coverage requiring
328 additional validation. Libraries and information managers can deploy visualization and
329 institutional monitoring services while promoting literacy and innovation, although
330 implementation demands complex data cleaning routines and developer support. Within

331 institutional frameworks and scientific policy evaluation, OpenAlex enables the construction
 332 of indicators aligned with international standards like DORA and CoARA while strengthening
 333 visibility for underrepresented areas and regions; however, the quality and completeness of
 334 metadata demand strict validation protocols and active management of structural biases.
 335 Finally, the technical and developer community benefits from API robustness and analytical
 336 customization, though encountering limits in query sophistication and interoperability with
 337 specialized platforms still under development.

338 Together, open infrastructures like OpenAlex support responsible evaluation agendas by
 339 democratizing access to bibliographic data and broadening epistemic diversity. Its
 340 consolidation will depend on progress in standardization and metadata enrichment,
 341 improvements in disambiguation through artificial intelligence, and the development of
 342 alternative metrics sensitive to social impact and equity. In 21st-century science, openness is
 343 not merely a technical condition but the guarantee that no voice or discipline is excluded from
 344 the scholarly record.

345 *Table 5. Opportunities and limitations of OpenAlex by user type*

User type	Opportunities	Limitations
Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Free and open access to resources that would normally be restricted - Agile incorporation of grey literature, preprints, and documents not indexed in traditional databases - Inclusion of new topics and approaches from emerging or lesser-known journals - Greater ease in identifying collaborations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Frequent errors and omissions in author and affiliation metadata, which can affect bibliographic tracking - Difficulty in delving into highly specialized areas due to partial coverage
Libraries and information managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dashboard and science mapping tools to deploy innovative and personalized visual services - Information literacy and training capabilities for internal and external users - Improved control and monitoring of institutional collections thanks to open workflows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complex cleaning and standardization routines to maintain the quality and updating of resources offered - Unequal institutional coverage in affiliation identification, affecting local visibility and benchmarking - Technical dependence on developers for integration with proprietary or third-party software
Academic institutions and evaluation agencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generation of indicators aligned with international agendas, promoting responsible evaluation, e.g., DORA and CoARA - Increased visibility for areas, disciplines, and the Global South that are traditionally underrepresented - Customization of scientific-technological monitoring based on institutional needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk of structural bias in evaluations due to lack of quality and completeness in key fields - Need for rigorous validation before using data in strategic decision-making
Technical profile and developer community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Robust API with options for developing personalized bibliometric tools and services - Simple integration with analysis languages and libraries (R, Python, scientific visualization software) - Facilitates experimentation and rapid prototyping for reproducible analysis in open source ecosystems - Possibility to create automated workflows for data collection, transformation, and exploitation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Restrictions in query sophistication and available metrics compared to advanced demands - Limited interoperability with institutional APIs or specialized platforms still under development

346 *Note: The opportunities and limitations presented here derive from the analysis conducted in this systematic review and reflect both empirical findings and*
 347 *practical implications identified in the literature.*

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